

Ainu

Data source: eHRAF

Secondary source

Entered by Emily Pitek, Human Relations Area Files

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** Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA*

Entry tags: Japanese Religions, Religion

The Ainu inhabit the island of Hokkaidō, which was incorporated into Japan in 1868. Contact with the Japanese did not influence traditional Ainu religious beliefs and practices until the late 1880's. This entry focuses on the Ainu living in Saru Basin, Hokkaidō around the time of 1880; before major cultural changes occurred as a result of Japanese influence. At this time, the Ainu religious beliefs and ritual practices were present in all dimensions of life; this entry considers the religious group to be coterminous with the society at large. Religious beliefs are generally animistic in nature, and a variety of supernatural beings are present and active in Ainu daily life.

Date Range: 1855 CE - 1880 CE

Region: Saru Basin, Hokkaido, Japan

Region tags: Asia, East Asia, Japan

Saru Basin, Hokkaido, Japan ca. 1880

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Murdock, G.P. & Wilson, S.F. (Jul., 1972). Settlement patterns and community organization: Cross-Cultural Codes 3. *Ethnology*, 11(3), 254-295.
- Source 1: Divale, W. 2004. Codebook of Variables for the Standard Cross-Cultural Sample. *World Cultures: The Journal of Cross-Cultural and Comparative Research*.
- Source 2: Murdock, G.P. (1967). *Ethnographic Atlas*. Pittsburgh, PA: University of Pittsburgh Press.
- Source 3: Tuden, A. & Marshall, C. (Oct., 1972). Political organization: Cross-cultural codes 4. *Ethnology*, 11(4), 436-464.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ab06-006>
- Source 1 Description: Sugiura, K. ichi, & Befu, H. (1962). Kinship Organization Of The Saru Ainu. *Ethnology*, 1, 287-298.
- Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ab06-000>
- Source 2 Description: Ohnuki-Tierney, E. (2009). *Culture Summary: Ainu*. New Haven, Conn.: Human

Relations Area Files.

– Source 1 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ab06-002>

– Source 1 Description: Batchelor, J. (1927). *Ainu Life And Lore: Echoes Of A Departing Race*. Tokyo: Kyobunkwan.

– Source 2 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ab06-011>

– Source 2 Description: Watanabe, H. (1964). *Ainu: A Study Of Ecology And The System Of Social Solidarity Between Man And Nature In Relation To Group Structure*. Journal. Tokyo: University of Tokyo.

– Source 3 URL: <http://ehrafworldcultures.yale.edu/document?id=ab06-007>

– Source 3 Description: Munro, N. G., Seligman, B. Z., & Watanabe, H. (1963). *Ainu Creed And Cult*. New York: Columbia University Press.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: "Contact between the Ainu and the Japanese, their southern neighbours, is of long standing, and for a considerable period the life of the Ainu had been subject to Japanese influence through what was called the 'basho' or district system that lasted from before 1789 to 1869. In 1868, Hokkaido came under the administration of the Japanese Government: the island became a part of the territory of Japan and colonization was started" (Watanabe, 1964:2). According to Watanabe (in Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:3), "The more general acceptance of agriculture by the Ainu, with the encouragement of the Japanese administration after 1884, resulted in considerable displacement of traditional groupings, since these had depended on areas suitable for fishing, hunting, and collecting, rather than on terrain suitable for farming. The old food-gathering system, especially that of hunting and fishing, had been closely linked with the religious beliefs of the Ainu. So long as it remained untouched, down to 1884, the religion of the Ainu remained intact, and the Japanese religious beliefs and practices made little headway."

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1649, Frequency of Internal Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that internal warfare seems to occur once every 3 to 10 years. Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Ainu are not completely pacified: some indication that warfare has decreased because of pacification attempts. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992; Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1650, Frequency of External Warfare (Resolved Rating), indicates that external warfare seems to be absent or rare. Additionally, SCCS Variable 1654, Pacification, indicates that the Ainu are not completely pacified: some indication that warfare has decreased because of pacification attempts. Source of information: Ember and Ember, 1992;

Retrieved from Divale, 2004.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is no system for assigning religious affiliation beyond being born into a particular lineage.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is no recruitment for new members.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: "It is impossible to describe any aspect of Ainu life without reference to ritual practices. The Ainu were, and many still are, saturated with animistic beliefs and these beliefs lead them to have recourse to ritual on so many occasions that some understanding of their relations with the spirit world is necessary for an adequate description of any aspect of their life. Social organization, hearth and home, hunting and fishing, festivals, disease, psychic ailments, medicines, birth, death and funeral observances—all demand some special reference to religious and magical procedures. To the Ainu all life is based on established beliefs, most of which involve supplication to the spirit powers in which they trust" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:7).

Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– Yes

Notes: SCCS Variable 1745 (Religio-political Overlap) indicates that officials at the level of maximal political authority are at the same time religious specialists (Hartmut, 1998; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: Because the religious group is coterminous with the society at large, there is no conception of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 16300

Notes: "The Ainu population of Hokkaido was estimated in 1940 at about 16,300 (NATORI, 1945, p. 280), a figure which has remained almost stable since 1854" (Watanabe, 1964:1).

– Estimated population, numeric: 160000

Notes: According to Watanabe, "In 1939 the Ainu population of Hokkaido was estimated at 160,000, and there had probably been little change since 1854. There were possibly another 10,000 scattered in the other islands" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:1).

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In addition to having political responsibilities, headmen had religious duties including leading rituals, supervising the proper observance of rituals and taboos, and knowing ancestral traditions (see Watanabe, 1964:12). In addition to headmen, shamans are present. However, shamans are not considered to be religious leaders. Rather, they are more accurately characterized as religious practitioners. "Among the Hokkaidō Ainu, shamanism is not highly regarded and shamans are usually women, who collectively have lower social status than men. The Hokkaidō Ainu shaman also enters a possession trance, but she does so only if a male elder induces it in her by offering prayers to the deities. Although she too diagnoses illnesses, male elders take over the healing process. Male elders must consult a shaman before they make important decisions for the community. In other words, the politically powerful male cannot even declare a war without consulting the shaman—an intriguing cultural mechanism to balance formalized and nonformalized power" (Ohnuki-Tierney, 2009).

– No

Notes: "The Ainu have no priesthood; the head of the family carries out the traditional ritual, and the home is the place of worship" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:7).

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of scriptures among the Ainu.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: "When I came first among [the Ainu], the people had no large buildings set apart as clubs, temples, or assembly rooms. That they had no temples does not mean that they had no religion, for what has been written in these chapters proves them to have been exceedingly religious. When there was a meeting to be held they assembled in the chief's hut" (Batchelor, 1927:37).

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Notes: "When I came first among [the Ainu], the people had no large buildings set apart as clubs,

temples, or assembly rooms. That they had no temples does not mean that they had no religion, for what has been written in these chapters proves them to have been exceedingly religious. When there was a meeting to be held they assembled in the chief's hut" (Batchelor, 1927:37).

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of pilgrimages.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: "In their idea no existing life can ever cease to be, whether it be good or evil, and immortality with them is as natural as nature itself" (Batchelor, 1927:152).

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Speaking of Heaven and Hell, one day a man said to me, 'The place to which good people go after death is called the home or land of the gods. There people live in a state of supreme happiness. Though they may be far away under our earth, they yet take a lively interest in what is going on among men living in this our upper world. Pokna shiri, i.e. 'the lower world,' is the place to which all spirits go upon leaving their earthly bodies. In the centre of this land there are three roads, the first leading to the upper world in which we now dwell. It goes right to the very centre of Hades, and every person born into this world must traverse this road at some time or other. The second and third roads also start from the middle of Hades and lead, one to Heaven and the other to Gehenna...As soon as the soul of a man gets to the place where the first watch-dog is stationed, the animal informs him that the Creator has sent word through the Goddess of Fire as to where he is to go. If he has been good during his life upon earth, he passes along to Heaven, at the gates of which place gods and men meet him and lead him in. But if it be the soul of a wicked person, a message has been received to say that he must go to Gehenna for punishment" (Batchelor, 1927:161).

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Notes: "When a child dies before it is weaned its ramat [spirit] is kept by Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of all departed spirits] until it can be reborn. Most elderly Ainu still believe that generation is not caused by the act of sexual intercourse but that it is due to the return of a soul from the Underworld under proper auspices" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:17).

In a human form:

– Yes

Notes: "When a child dies before it is weaned its ramat [spirit] is kept by Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of all departed spirits] until it can be reborn. Most elderly Ainu still believe that generation is not caused by the act of sexual intercourse but that it is due to the return of a soul from the Underworld under proper auspices" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:17).

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of reincarnation in animal/plant form.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Notes: "The mourners follow the dead in single file, the men leading; each carrying something to be buried with the body. Whatever the distance to the grave may be, it is the custom, in some districts, to rest three times on the way. The grave is usually dug about three feet deep. [Page 159] Stakes are driven round the inside to which mats are hung. The earth is then thrown in and some branches covered over it" (Batchelor, 1927:158).

↳ Cremation:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cremation.

↳ Mummification:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mummification.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: "The mourners follow the dead in single file, the men leading; each carrying something to be buried with the body. Whatever the distance to the grave may be, it is the custom, in some districts, to rest three times on the way. The grave is usually dug about three feet deep. [Page 159] Stakes are driven round the inside to which mats are hung. The earth is then thrown in and some branches covered over it" (Batchelor, 1927:158).

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of cannibalism.

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of exposing corpses to the elements.

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of feeding corpses to animals.

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 1850 (Secondary Bone/Body Treatment: Original Scale) indicates that secondary contact with the body or bones of the deceased does not occur (Schroeder, 2001; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of co-sacrifices.

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Notes: "Should the deceased be a man, his bow, arrows and quiver, his pipe, tobacco-box, fire sticks and tinder or flint and steel for obtaining light, a long and short knife, a sword, a cup and tray, moustache-lifters and a small bundle of clothes are placed by his side. The clothes are cut or torn and the other things broken or chipped. All these articles are buried with the body. The cutting, chipping and breaking are said to be done in order to kill the things and send their spirits off to heaven with the corpse" (Batchelor, 1927:155). "Should the corpse be that of a woman, some needles and thread, some native and Japanese clothes of various colours and kinds, a set of weaving implements, spoons, ladles and cups, and her trinkets, such as beads and earrings, are placed by her side. Children also have a cup, a spoon, some clothes, toys, and trinkets placed by them. They are all damaged in some way and then buried with their former owner. Thus the dead one is sent away well provided" (Batchelor, 1937:156).

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Notes: (Batchelor, 1927:155-156)

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: (Batchelor, 1927:155-156)

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: (Batchelor, 1927:155-156)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: "The mourners follow the dead in single file, the men leading; each carrying something to be buried with the body. Whatever the distance to the grave may be, it is the custom, in some districts, to rest three times on the way. The grave is usually dug about three feet deep. [Page 159] Stakes are driven round the inside to which mats are hung. The earth is then thrown in and some branches covered over it" (Batchelor, 1927:158). For further descriptions of Ainu burial practices, see Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:132-134.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: "In the past Ainu had no graveyards, burial in spots round the village being the rule. As we have seen, elders were sometimes buried near the house. But there have been graveyards for many years..." (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:133).

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: "While a rigid classification of kamui [spirits], recognized as such by the Ainu, is not feasible, some arrangement will aid description. It need hardly be said that in polytheistic religions there is much latitude in choosing gods for general, as well as for special help, so long as this does not reflect upon the standing of any god worshiped by the community in general. Though there are some places where such preference is marked, in no place visited by me is the ancestral cult with its concomitant worship of the hearth spirit neglected for other kamui. The following classification is proposed: 1. Remote and traditional kamui. 2. Familiar or accessible and trustworthy kamui. 3. Subsidiary kamui. 4. Theriomorphic kamui. 5. Spirit helpers and personal kamui. 6. Mischievous and malicious kamui. 7. Kamui of pestilence. 8. Things of unutterable horror" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:11).

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], indicates that a high god is absent among the Ainu (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: "...the people believe that the souls of human beings will have a conscious, personal existence after death..." (Batchelor, 1927:162).

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: "When they [the spirits of the deceased] come to us they are invisible to our

eyes..." (Batchelor, 1927:162).

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "Deceased friends and ancestors are supposed to be present at times among the people they have left behind. Though unseen, they are able to render material assistance to the living, or to afflict them if they think they deserve it" (Batchelor, 1927:3).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: "Deceased friends and ancestors are supposed to be present at times among the people they have left behind. Though unseen, they are able to render material assistance to the living, or to afflict them if they think they deserve it. Sometimes they appear to men in dreams, either to warn or encourage them. It is also believed that gods, demons and men sometimes appear to the living in the assumed forms of birds, fishes, bears and other animals, to deliver messages. When their purpose has been accomplished, these return immediately to their proper, natural form" (Batchelor, 1927:3).

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: See Batchelor, 1927:3

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– Yes [specify]: In the form of animals

Notes: Batchelor, 1927:3

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: "The fire as it exists upon the hearth and in volcanoes also has often been spoken of in these chapters as being a Goddess who is frequently worshiped. She is indeed a very important deity and figures much in Ainu thought and religion. She is called Huchi or Fuji, which means 'Old Woman' and 'Grandmother.'" (Batchelor, 1927:175). "All members of a patrilineal descent group worshipped the same guardian deity, known as pase-onkami. The deities worshipped were the bear, owl, fox, dolphin, etc. The Ainu believed that these deities had once been protectors of their ancestors" (Sugiura and Befu, 1962:291).

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: "It is also believed that gods, demons and men sometimes appear to the living in the assumed forms of birds, fishes, bears and other animals, to deliver messages. When their purpose has been accomplished, these return immediately to their proper, natural form" (Batchelor, 1927:3).

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: "As I understand it, Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed] is the judge who punishes any misconduct, ritual or ethical, in this life by visiting upon the offender some misfortune or withdrawing her protection against evil spirits" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Notes: "As I understand it, Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed] is the judge who punishes any misconduct, ritual or ethical, in this life by visiting upon the offender some misfortune or withdrawing her protection against evil spirits" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of mixed human-divine beings.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: "While a rigid classification of kamui [spirits], recognized as such by the Ainu, is not feasible, some arrangement will aid description. It need hardly be said that in polytheistic religions there is much latitude in choosing gods for general, as well as for special help, so long as this does not reflect upon the standing of any god worshiped by the community in general. Though there are some places where such preference is marked, in no place visited by me is the ancestral cult with its concomitant worship of the hearth spirit neglected for other kamui. The following classification is proposed: 1. Remote and traditional kamui. 2. Familiar or accessible and trustworthy kamui. 3. Subsidiary kamui. 4. Theriomorphic kamui. 5. Spirit helpers and personal kamui. 6. Mischievous and malicious kamui. 7. Kamui of pestilence. 8. Things of unutterable horror" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:11).

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: While supernatural monitoring is not described in detail, Kamui Fuchi (deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed) as well as spirits of the deceased, are described as punishing the living for misconduct (see Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18; and Batchelor, 1927:3).

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: "As I understand it, Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed] is the judge who punishes any misconduct, ritual or ethical, in this life by visiting upon the offender some misfortune or withdrawing her protection against evil spirits" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of deceased humans are described as agents of supernatural punishment

(Batchelor, 1927:3), as well as Kamui Fuchi (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Notes: According to SCCS Variable 238, Religion: High Gods [note, identical to Ethnographic Atlas variable 34], indicates that a high god is absent among the Ainu (Murdock, 1962-1971; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The spirits of deceased humans are described as agents of supernatural punishment (Batchelor, 1927:3), as well as Kamui Fuchi (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: "As I understand it, Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed] is the judge who punishes any misconduct, ritual or ethical, in this life by visiting upon the offender some misfortune or withdrawing her protection against evil spirits" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: "As I understand it, Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed] is the judge who punishes any misconduct, ritual or ethical, in this life by visiting upon the offender some misfortune or withdrawing her protection against evil spirits" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

↳ Done randomly:

– No

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Speaking of Heaven and Hell, one day a man said to me, 'The place to which good people go after death is called the home or land of the gods. There people live in a state of supreme happiness. Though they may be far away under our earth, they yet take a lively interest in what is going on among men living in this our upper world. Pokna shiri, i.e. 'the lower world,' is the place to which all spirits go upon leaving their earthly bodies. In the centre of this land there are three roads, the first leading to the upper world in which we now dwell. It goes right to the very centre of Hades, and every person born into this world must traverse this road at some time or other. The second and third roads also start from the middle of Hades and lead, one to Heaven and the other to Gehenna...As soon as the soul of a man gets to the place where the first watch-dog is stationed, the animal informs him that the Creator has sent

word through the Goddess of Fire as to where he is to go. If he has been good during his life upon earth, he passes along to Heaven, at the gates of which place gods and men meet him and lead him in. But if it be the soul of a wicked person, a message has been received to say that he must go to Gehenna for punishment" (Batchelor, 1927:161).

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife is present, but not described in detail.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife is present, but not described in detail.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– I don't know

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife is present, but not described in detail.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– I don't know

Notes: Punishment in the afterlife is present, but not described in detail.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: "As I understand it, Kamui Fuchi [deity of fire and ruler of spirits of the departed] is the judge who punishes any misconduct, ritual or ethical, in this life by visiting upon the offender some misfortune or withdrawing her protection against evil spirits" (Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:18).

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of messianic beliefs.

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of an eschatology.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of fasting.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of required painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of human sacrifice.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Notes: Small-scale rituals are present (such as family worship of patrilineal descent group guardian deities, see Sugiura and Befu, 1962:291), but it is not clear if participation is mandatory.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: "Among the rich and complex Ainu religious beliefs and practices, the bear ceremony is perhaps the most important religious ceremony among both the Sakhalin and Hokkaidō Ainu, for whom the bear represents the supreme deity in disguise. From the Ainu perspective, the bear ceremony is a 'funeral ritual' for the bear. Its purpose is to send the soul of the bear back to the mountains through a proper ritual so the soul will be reborn as a bear and revisit the Ainu with gifts of meat and fur" (Ohnuki-Tierney, 2009). For more information on the bear ceremony, see Munro, Seligman, and Watanabe, 1963:169-171; Batchelor, 1927:205-211; Watanabe, 1964:73, 75-76.

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The bear keeper leads the bear ceremony (See Watanabe, 1964:75-76).

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Notes: See below for more details on extra-ritual in-group markers.

Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: "The women said, 'The divine sister of Aeoina taught us that if any woman marries a man without first being tattooed in a proper manner, she commits a great sin, and when she dies will go straight to hell.' The men said, 'Untattooed women may not take part in any feast, for to do so would mean dishonouring the gods and men alike. Indeed, it would bring down the wrath of heaven upon both themselves and the assembled guests. Women untattooed go to hell when they die, and upon getting there the demons assemble with big knives and do all the tattooing at one sitting.' This indeed, would be very painful" (Batchelor, 1927:49).

↳ Ornaments:

– Yes

Notes: "Underneath her clothes every adolescent or mature Ainu woman wore a belt, called upshor (Segawa 1952). This belt was never to be shown or talked about, and a great deal of magical belief was associated with it. Women who belonged to the same matrilineal group wore belts which were made in the same manner and differed from those worn by women of other descent groups. The belt was thus the symbol and proof of membership in the matrilineal group, as the ancestral crest was of the patrilineal group" (Sugiura and Befu, 1962:293).

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A tribe

Notes: The Ainu have one level of jurisdictional hierarchy beyond the local community, which is reflective of a small chiefdom (Ethnographic Atlas column 33, Murdock, 1967; retrieved from Divale, 2004). Contradictory to this information, according to Murdock and Wilson (1972; Column 10: Descent), the Ainu have double descent (both patrilineal and matrilineal) with dispersed sibs. Additionally, the Ainu lived in demes, with matrilineal lineages of modest size. Source of information: Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1967), Columns 19, 20, 22. Further, Watanabe, (1964:16) describes the Ainu as having a river groups, which are aggregations of local groups living along a river. These river groups are linked both ritually and economically. Bearing all this information in mind, the Ainu are best characterized as a tribe.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Insufficient ethnographic information.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence indicating that the Ainu had a formal bureaucracy.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 20, Food Storage, indicates that food is stored in individual households (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004).

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Notes: SCCS Variable 14, Routes of Land Transport, indicates that unimproved trails are used (Murdock and Morrow, 1970; Retrieved from Divale, 2004). Consequently, it can be inferred that the Ainu do not have a transportation infrastructure.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Notes: No ethnographic evidence for the presence of taxes or tithes among the Ainu.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 10, Police) "police functions are not specialized or institutionalized at any level of political integration, the maintenance of law and order being left exclusively to informal mechanisms of social control, to private retaliation, or to sorcery." [Note: identical to SCCS Variable 90].

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: According to Tuden and Marshall (1972; Column 9, Judiciary), "supreme judicial authority is lacking at any level above that of the local community." [Note: Identical to SCCS Variable 89].

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The Ainu rely primarily on hunting and fishing for subsistence. The diet is supplemented by hunting and extensive/shifting agriculture. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.

↳ Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

Notes: The Ainu rely primarily on hunting and fishing for subsistence. The diet is supplemented by hunting and extensive/shifting agriculture. Source of information from Ethnographic Atlas (Murdock, 1962-1971), retrieved from Divale, 2004; Variables 203-207, 232.